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Assessment of Nature-Based Solutions Implementation Practice

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Abbreviations

EID - Environmental Identity
EU - European Union
INS - Inclusion of Nature in Self
LLs - Living Labs
NBG - Nature-based Governance
NBS - Nature-based Solutions
WBC - Community Well-being
WBI - Well-being Indicators
WTP - Willingness to Pay

Executive summary

Governance of Nature-based Solutions embodies a holistic approach that acknowledges the intrinsic and relational values of nature, aiming to align human activities with ecological systems for sustainable development and long-term well-being. *Despite broad applications*, there are barriers to NBS's widespread implementation that hinder its effectiveness and scalability. *The objective of this deliverable is to assess current socio-political challenges in NBS design and implementation practice with a special focus on the vulnerability of humans and non-human species, and to create an institutional typology of nature-based governance.*

D.4.1. is explorative to provide hermeneutic understanding about the problematic situations in seven LL sites and articulate and form hypotheses or questions for future, broader scale scientific work on the societal, environmental, and institutional conditions of NBS design and implementation. It builds on the study from seven COEVOLVERs LLs' learning communities in eight European countries (Czech Republic and Slovakia, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Finland, Estonia, and Scotland) with a completed survey with the general public and interviews with key stakeholders. The study underlined high connectivity to nature in all the LLs, which provided motivation for pro-nature action and highlighted the barriers and benefits in implementing NBS and deriving promising NBS potential for LLs communities, including vulnerable and other than human agencies. This forms the basis for conceptual work on nature-based governance that manifests the interconnection of physical and social domains, concerning vulnerable agencies *to include LLs into the co-creation of nature-based governance models* and allocating rights to other than human species. The benefit of such governance mode is to address sustainability challenges by working with nature to identify institutional solutions that can tweak the coevolution of institutions and the environment into more sustainable directions. D.4.1. as work in progress will further inform the institutional reconfiguration (D.4.2) and co-creation of nature-based governance models (D.4.3). Furthermore, forthcoming survey under the T.3.4. will complement analyses in measuring attitudes, beliefs and motivations on a broader scale, The survey will also meet the requirements of random sampling and representativeness, and hence it will provide further interpretative support for the D.4.1. survey results.

Introduction

Nature-based solutions (NBS) have emerged as a promising approach to address societal and global sustainability challenges, particularly in the context of climate change and biodiversity loss. Supported by and copied from nature, NBS aim to

overcome ecological, social, and economic challenges (Schroter et al. 2022). In the EU, NBS are favoured because, when properly designed and implemented, they are expected to be cost-effective in providing environmental, social, and economic benefits, and have long-term socio-ecological resilience (European Commission 2023). NBS have been shown to be effective in various land management practices, including organic farming, land restoration, sediment trapping, rewilding, and wetland construction, offering cost-effective long-term solutions for hydrological risks and land degradation (Keesstra et al., 2018). While NBS hold promise in protecting against climate change impacts, supporting biodiversity, and securing ecosystem services, barriers to their widespread implementation need to be addressed to maximise their benefits (Seddon et al., 2020). This is the question that initiated COEVOLVERS to critically study the socio-politics of the design and implementation of NBS governance.

Governance is typically understood as the coordination of multilayered social relations and processes in the absence of a unifying authority (Rhodes, 1996). In environmental governance, the integration of natural elements with societal ones is motivated by the aim to collaboratively tackle environmental challenges while fostering social and economic development (Dupuits, 2015; Asamoah & Maina, 2022). The interconnection of human activities, other species, and their living environments establishes the ground for ensuring that NBS practices benefit society and ecosystems (Buijs et al 2024). NBS governance is therefore a unique approach within the family of environmental governance, aimed at achieving sustainable and inclusive outcomes that benefit both human and non-human wellbeing and health.

Governance encompasses a diverse range of approaches that involve stakeholder collaboration, community engagement and reflexivity to effectively implement environmental and societal solutions. Among such approaches, reflexive governance emphasizes social-ecological vulnerabilities and sustainability transitions in the face of risks and uncertainties (Feindt & Weiland, 2018), whilst collaborative governance, such as network or hybrid governance widely adopted to manage complex natural resource issues (Olvera-Garcia & Sipe, 2019), is a dynamic and adaptive approach that fosters cooperation and social learning at various levels, from local to international. Another more recent approach is transformative governance, which builds on the co-production of knowledge for the renewal of belief systems and underlying societal goals, thus turning participation-emphasising collaborative governance and administration-driven mindsets into co-creative learning communities (Wickenberg et al., 2022).

The governance aspects of NBS are increasingly acknowledged as crucial, with growing emphasis on governance in research papers related to NBS (Li et al., 2021).

Robust governance mechanisms are essential to ensure that NBS is responsive to the needs and preferences of local communities, promoting inclusivity and accountability (Chausson et al., 2023). Governance, financing, and business models are interconnected, and play a significant role in the successful implementation of urban NBS (Egusquiza et al., 2021).

There are various examples of stakeholders' involvement in environmental governance, e.g. the interaction between public and private actors (Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020), citizens' participation to ensure long-term sustainability and social inclusivity (Kiss et al., 2022), and community-based natural resource management (Dale et al., 2020). A crucial factor influencing natural resource governance at various levels, from international agreements to local community arrangements, is inequality (Ravnborg & Gómez, 2015). By integrating fairness and stability, governance can enhance transparency and accountability in the decision-making processes related to natural resource management and environmental protection.

However, it is known that NBS do not equally reach all potential beneficiaries: NBS have socio-political challenges that affect their functioning, uptake and impacts. For instance, understanding and addressing vulnerabilities in NBS has become a key topic in governance and management that aims to increase effectiveness. To address the socio-politics of NBS, governance models, techniques and practices call for critical scrutiny to make modifications for inclusiveness and responsiveness for the needs of those who live and work in circumstances that produce vulnerability (see, e.g. Wang et al., 2022). Vulnerability-producing circumstances require specific governance measures to protect the sovereignty, autonomy, and individuality of people, but also non-human agencies (Honkasalo, 2018) while fulfilling demands to establish novel institutional positions and rights (Upadhyay, 2021). In this, vulnerability assessments can help identify sensitive groups that live in circumstances that produce vulnerability and which hence struggle to respond to and recover from environmental hazards (Cutter & Finch, 2008). These assessments need to consider the dynamic and complex nature of vulnerability, which can vary over time, space, and among different social groups (Cutter et al., 2003). In the context of disasters like pandemics and climate change, identifying and reaching vulnerability can be challenging due to the diverse and context-dependent nature of vulnerability (Joseph et al., 2023). Vulnerability can thus be considered a transdisciplinary term "affecting but also effecting" and opening up to something unexpected that matters (Lecourt, 2002).

This not only calls for a radical change in governance practices but, in addition, a clearer understanding of the socio-ecological systems under threat (Moore & Tjornbo, 2012). Such rethinking can lead to more informed and actionable outcomes to fight

the conditions that produce vulnerability (Rossignol et al., 2014). Factors such as socioeconomic status and governance quality can significantly influence vulnerability levels among different population groups (Rasch, 2015). It is crucial to consider the specific requirements of vulnerable groups concerning disaster-resilient communities (Margarena, 2023).

The consideration of species other than humans in designing and implementing NBS is gaining prominence. Already Schlosberg (2007) emphasized the need for a comprehensive notion of justice that encompasses not only human populations but also the interactions between human communities, other species and their shared living environments. This kind of holistic multispecies approach aims to recognise the variety of different values in problematic environmental situations, adding a new layer of complexity to the analysis of socio-politics of NBS (Buijs et al. 2024).

Environmental governance faces various barriers that hinder the effective and scalable implementation of models, techniques and practices. In this regard, common obstacles have been identified in literature, such as funding, integration challenges, difficulties in finding suitable suppliers, and limited knowledge gaps (Kabisch et al., 2016; Sarabi et al., 2020). These obstacles can also impede the uptake and implementation of NBS, limiting its potential impact on addressing environmental issues. The main barriers to implementing NBS can be clustered into four categories: i) legislation-policymaking misfit (e.g. land use practices, property issues, conflicting policies), ii) social practices, knowledge values and habits, iii) communication, awareness, and iv) financial and administrative. This is in line with the findings of the seven COEVOLVERS National Consultation Groups assessment process conducted and reported in (Pihlajamäki et al., 2024). That report identifies the following key barriers of NBS implementation: knowledge, values and expertise, communication and cross-sectoral coordination, participation and community awareness, financing, planning, and policy support. Understanding the socio-politics of NBS and responding to vulnerability-producing circumstances are key objectives of COEVOLVERS.

For COEVOLVERS, NBS governance embodies a holistic approach that acknowledges the intrinsic values of nature, aiming to align human activities with ecological systems for sustainable development and long-term well-being. Addressing the governance challenges associated with NBS implementation is therefore crucial to unlock the full potential of these solutions. Developing robust governance mechanisms, engaging vulnerable groups, including species other than humans effectively, and ensuring financial sustainability are the key aspects that need to be considered in order to facilitate the successful out-scaling of NBS initiatives for human and non-human well-being.

The objective of this deliverable is to assess the current socio-political challenges in NBS design and implementation practice with a special focus on the vulnerability of humans and non-human species, and to create an institutional typology of nature-based governance.

Section 2 introduces an empirical context of seven Living Lab areas, materials, methods. Section 3 analyses existing practices and explores people’s attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions on the relation with their living environments, the role of NBS in individual and community well-being, and potential barriers and benefits in implementing NBS.

Section 4 introduces the resulting institutional typology and the concept of nature-based governance. Section 5 concludes.

2 Introducing the Empirical Context

2.1. Coevolvers Living Labs (LLs)

COEVOLVERS Living Labs (LLs) are seven “communities of inquiry” in eight European countries (Czech Republic and Slovakia, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Finland, Estonia, and Scotland). LLs with three different stages of NBS (existed, incipient, emerging) are set to co-create novel approaches to NBS design and implementation. They also test the new tools and governance models applicable for NBS governance models. The key governance of the seven LLs is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Governance in the seven COEVOLVERS LLs.

Defining NBS	Problem situation	Governance	Affordances
Social and ecological compensation in Pansio Perno - Turku, Finland (Turku)	Construction of urban green space and the consequent urban nature loss causes negative impacts on individual and social well-being and health, both human and non-human.	Network governance to support urban biodiversity recovery and multidimensional human well-being and health via eco-social compensation including social, cultural, and experiential values of nature in urban planning practices.	River acts as a movement route for different non-humans. In heterogeneous area with forest, coastal meadows, as well as different types of housing (including refugees), industries and harbours.
Natural Connections in	Inequal access to nature and habitual	Network governance for community-cohesion	Woodland Park is a diverse woodland

Murray Park - Scotland, UK (Scotland)	disconnection from nature are key challenges in land use. Cultivating a reflective, emotionally and intellectually motivated connection.	between humans and nature built on an incipient reflective understanding of and affinity for natural features, habitats and affordances with nature fosters a sense of harmony, well-being and moral growth. Participants act as custodians, care-takers and safe-guarders thereof.	ecosystem with low human influence. The area has recreational and mental (“site of belonging”) affordances for humans, and provides rich living habitat for various woodland species.
Committing to diversity in Molentargius Saline Regional Nature Park, Cagliari - Sardinia, Italy (Sardinia)	Ecosystems, their local populations, and biodiversity of natural parks close to urban areas are often accidentally and purposefully threatened by human activities.	Collaborative (polycentric) governance of urban park engages different types of social groups, such as older and younger people, potentially to gain a symbiotic relationship between various human and non-human uses.	The LL area in the Molentargius-Saline Regional Park is a large saline lagoon near the city of Cagliari in Sardinia. It is a biodiversity hotspot- Ramsar site important for pink flamingos and local and migratory water birds, amphibians and reptiles, as well as a vacation and recreation area for people.
Virtual commons in Beskydy – Czechia and Slovakia (Beskydy)	Existing nature-based solutions are often implemented as 'technological fixes' to environmental problems, producing vulnerability and marginalisation. In cross-border communities, the problem is especially pressing.	Virtual commons is a climate-smart common pool resource regime being developed for the watershed promoting behavioural change and the resilience of cross-border community via the digital platform beskydyonline.eu	Beskydy's main affordance is pine forest exposed to climate change with the presence of wild animal species (rich biodiversity), including predators such as wolves.
Reducing wildfires by grazing in Catalonia - Spain (Catalonia)	Wildfires are causing increasingly damage and harm to humans and nature across Europe and beyond. Increasingly adaptive measures to mitigate damages, novel land use, and farming practices are initiated.	Ecosystem service payment (PES) schemes supporting fire “eaters” sheep grazing practices while providing continuity for sheep farming livelihoods as part of hybrid governance .	LL area is agro-pasture system with sheep as non-human agency to prevent wildfires. Other affordances are sites of good pasture, shelter and drinking water.
Multispecies city in Tartu - Estonia (Tartu)	Urban wildlife thrives on environments that are of ecological quality, but urban nature is mostly designed from the point of view of human preferences, needs, and aesthetics which often	Multispecies community of gardens and biodiversity-friendly gardening via network governance .	The area provides living place, access to wildlife and recreation for humans. The main affordances to non-humans are diverse

	does not align with non-human species' needs.		living habitat and ecological corridors.
Healing garden in Hungary (Hungary)	Mental health and well-being are connected with the quality of/access to the everyday environment and. Not all people live near equally accessible environmental quality.	Collaborative healing garden community to be co-created with the health care institute, clients, their families, health care professionals, and environmental/ gardening experts.	Healing garden in a mental healthcare institute provides a place for activities that support healing (meditation, relaxation) and various contacts with non-human species.

Note: Names in brackets are abbreviated names of LLs for the purpose of this analysis rather than geographical units.

2.2. Materials and methods

2.2.1. Procedures and samples

Two data sets were gathered from two sample kinds: **qualitative data** stemmed from semi-structured face-to-face interviews with key LL stakeholders; **quantitative data** was collected through a questionnaire (face-to-face or online) with general public around the LL, i.e. individuals visiting an LL or living in the city/area with an LL.

The first sample included interviews with 77 key stakeholders (F=52.6%) of the seven LLs. Most stakeholders (45%) were aged 45–59, 35% 30–44, 19% 60–75, and 1% 18–29. Interview participants were on the whole highly educated: 9% with secondary education, 63% with university degree, and 24% with PhD). Regarding employment, 23% were business representatives, 17% municipal authority, 12% academics, 10% state authorities, 8% regional authorities, while 31% of stakeholders have multiple positions.

The second sample comprised 365 general public survey participants around the LL (e.g. residents and visitors from LLs, F=67.9%). The age ranges were as follows: 35% 45–59, 27% 30–44, 24% 60-75, and 13% 18–29. Three participants (1%) did not provide their age. The educational level of survey participants was as follows: 38% secondary education, 34% university degree, and 20% PhD. Employment: 24% public employees, 23% business people, 6% university staff, 16% service-providers, and 29% 'other'. In analysing the survey results, we excluded Hungary participants due to the small sample size (only six participants). Hence the final sample consisted of 359 participants. All survey/interview respondents participated on a voluntary basis after signing an informed consent related to their research contribution.

D4.1 is explorative, since its aim is to provide hermeneutic understanding about the problematic situations in the seven LL sites. Representativeness will be addressed in the meso-level survey conducted in T3.4. In this case, a higher-scale level stratified sampling will be conducted around the LL areas, covering for instance Turku metropolitan area (instead of Pansio-Perno neighborhood) and wider border regions in Czech-border area than just Beskydy. D3.4. (Measuring attitudes, beliefs and motivations) will then provide further interpretative support for the D.4.1. survey.

2.2.2 Tools and measures

Both the survey with the general public and the semi-structured face-to-face interviews with key LL stakeholders had overlapping and specific measures. Overlapping measures included: *Inclusion of Nature in the Self (INS)*, *Environmental Identity (EID)*, *Individual Well-Being (WBI)*, *Community Well-Being (WBC)*.

INS is a one-dimensional, graphical tool adapted by Schultz (2002) from the Inclusion of Others in the Self Scale by Aron et al. (1992). *INS* involves perceiving similarities between oneself and the natural world, assuming that individuals who define themselves as part of nature have cognitive representations of self-overlapping with the interpretation of nature, fostering attachment (Clayton & Myers, 2009; Schultz, 2001). This relationship is often explained by the biophilia hypothesis, asserting that human reliance on nature extends beyond material sustenance, encompassing aesthetic, intellectual, cognitive, and spiritual fulfilment. Thus, the environment contributes to satisfying basic psychological needs and fostering self-knowledge (Kellert, 1993; Clayton, 2003). It depicts the relationship between the Self and Nature, with a graphical representation consisting of two circles that are progressively overlapping, from 1 = distant to 7 = full overlay (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Measuring Inclusion of Nature in the Self (*INS*).

EID includes 10 items (see Table 2) adapted from the Revised Environmental Identity Scale, EID-R (Clayton et al., 2021). The EID construct concerns the belief that the environment is integral to one's identity (Clayton, 2003), and assumes a sense of interdependence and connectedness with nature, considering both the cognitive and emotional facets of people's relationship with the natural world. Items were rated on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 = not true according to me to 7 = completely true to me. The scale's internal reliability was good (Cronbach's Alpha=.86).

Table 2. *Environmental Identity Scale.*

2.1. I like to spend time outdoors in nature (woods, mountains, rivers, local parks, lake or beach, or garden).
2.2 I think of myself as separate from nature, not a part of it.
2.3. When I am upset, stressed, or feel unhealthy, I can feel better by spending some time outdoors surrounded by nature.
2.4. If I had enough resources such as time or money, I would spend some of them to protect the natural environment.
2.5. I am not that interested in being in nature.
2.6. Behaving responsibly towards nature -- living a sustainable lifestyle -- is important to who I am.
2.7. Learning about the natural world should be part of everyone's upbringing.
2.8. If I could choose, I would prefer to live where I can have a view of the natural environment, such as trees or fields.
2.9. I think elements of the natural world are more beautiful than any work of art.
2.10. I enjoy encountering elements of nature, like trees or grass, even when I am in a city.

WBI is represented by the question: "Which of the following currently contributes to your well-being? (tick those which apply)" and a check-all-that-apply (CATA) answer format structured with nine factors (e.g. nature providing opportunities for foraging, hunting, fishing).

WBC is represented by the question: "Which of the following currently contributes to the wellbeing of your local community? (tick those which apply)" and a check-all-that-apply (CATA) answer format structured with six factors (e.g. halting biodiversity loss - protecting fauna, flora).

Specific tools and measures for the general public sample

Willingness to pay (WTP) to improve the relationship to nature in the local community: This variable was measured with one question: "How much are you willing to pay to improve the relationship to nature in your community". Four answer options were provided, i.e. EUR 5–10; EUR 11–20; EUR 21–50; and EUR 50+. This question was optional. Those who responded were also asked about the *appropriateness of fund sources*, with one choice from five options (e.g. community fee to cover upkeep of nature and ecosystem).

Specific tools and measures for LL key stakeholders

Key LL stakeholders responded to face-to-face interviews differently than the general public. In fact, beside the face-to-face mode (rather than online), key stakeholders were asked to answer questions during an in-depth interview and to “think aloud” in order to motivate their choices. Specific measures were as follows.

Knowledge about barriers/obstacles to NBS implementation in the local community is represented by one question: “Are you aware of any barriers/obstacles to implementing NBS in your community?” and a check-all-that-apply (CATA) answer format structured with 13 factors (e.g. property rights affecting land access/use).

Economics of NBS in the Living Lab context is represented by two questions: “What mechanisms exist to financially support NBS in your LL in general?” and a check-all-that-apply (CATA) answer format structured with four factors (e.g. public compensations/subsidies). Second concerns: “What role does funding play in developing successful NBA in your LL?” and a check-all-that-apply (CATA) answer format structured with five factors (e.g. Funding not needed or can be complementary).

Benefits related to NBS is represented by one question: “Thinking about your context, please rate how much you think each benefit is important for your local community”, followed by a list of 10 items (e.g. biodiversity and wildlife) evaluated on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 = not important at all, to 7 = very important.

Transformative Potential of NBS is represented by the question: “Please indicate which of the options below could support the implementation/development of NBS towards positive changes in your context?”, followed by 10 items (e.g. Adaptive-shared-management (more members involved - collective responsibility). Participants could choose only four in order of importance.

2.2.3 Statistical Analyses

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were run. Descriptive analyses were carried out on data collected from both samples. Specifically, the mean scores of INS and EID measures were computed for each Living Lab in the two samples. An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was also performed on the EID scale.

Inferential analyses were run only for the survey sample, since the interview sample was too small to achieve reliable results (and indeed such sample was planned mainly to collect qualitative data). These analyses included bivariate correlations between variables, and Multivariate Analyses of Variance (MANOVAs), with Bonferroni post-hoc test, where LL was a between-subject factor (with seven levels), and EID and INS scores were the dependent variables. Correspondence Analysis was then performed to assess the association between LLs and the number of selections made in two questions: 1. Choices made toward Individual Well-Being (WBI), 2. Choices made toward Community Well-Being (WBC). This statistical technique was designed to uncover patterns and relationships within LLs (categorical variables) and the array of choices made in the selected areas. Simultaneously, this analysis allows for visually organizing highlighted associations within the same dimensional space (Lana et al., 2017). Drawing on contingency tables, CA leverages the frequencies of rows and columns (encompassing categorical and nominal variables) to position them in a geometric space, relying on Chi-square distances. Increased proximity between points on the map indicates a more robust association between variables in the rows and columns (Harcar & Spillan, 2006; Kaynak & Kucukemiroglu, 2001). The dimensions that emerged in the CA can be understood by identifying the primary contributors to the explained variance along each axis. The proportion of variance explained by each dimension is referred to as singular value (Beldona et al., 2005). Finally, a Kruskal Wallis Chi-square test was performed for the financial mechanism and phases of funding. All the statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS for Windows version 27.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL 60606) and MS Excel.

3. NBS implementation practice in seven LLs

3.1 Human-Nature relationship in LLs

INS (Schultz et al. 2002) and EID (adapted from Clayton et al., 2021) measures show how the general public of LL areas (i.e. the survey respondents) and LL key stakeholders (i.e. interviewees) showed their connection with the environments. Table 3 reports the means and standard deviations of INS and EID in the seven LLs.

Table 3. INS and EID mean values and standard deviations for the seven LLs (general public and key stakeholders).

Mean values and standard deviations				
N: general public/key stakeholders	INS general public	INS key stakeholders	EID general public	EID key stakeholders

		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Turku (1)	48/10	5.25	0.96	5.60	0.52	6.10	0.88	6.29	0.47
Scotland (2)	65/13	5.38	1.06	6.15	0.80	6.32	0.68	6.60	0.37
Sardinia (3)	85/12	4.68	1.21	5.67	0.89	6.21	0.82	6.33	0.44
Beskydy (4)	54/11	5.02	1.49	6.09	0.83	6.54	0.49	6.48	0.47
Catalonia (5)	51/9	5.43	1.45	4.89	1.36	6.49	0.59	Na	Na
Tartu (6)	61/10	4.33	1.57	4.80	1.32	5.98	0.94	6.20	0.59
Hungary (7)	06/12	Na	Na	5.42	1.08	Na	Na	6.49	0.25

Note: Names of LLs are illustrative for the purpose of this analysis rather than geographical units

The mean values of INS were 4.92 for the general public and 5.67 for the key stakeholders. This difference is not surprising given the expected higher involvement and understanding related to nature issues of key stakeholders compared to the general public. More generally, mean values in both samples were higher than those reported in previous studies (Bruni & Schultz, 2010; Schultz & Tabanico 2007). For comparison, Schultz and Tabanico (2007) reported that the INS mean score among American college students was 3.31, and slightly higher scores emerged in a sample of visitors to San Diego Zoo (M = 4.92 to 5.14 across three studies). Like INS average scores, mean values of EID, respectively 6.26 for the general public and 6.74 for core stakeholders, were higher than those commonly found in previous studies (see Clayton et al., 2021 for comparison). Thus, we observe a roof effect of EID scale distribution. This is probably due to the fact that our sample of key stakeholders is by definition typically composed of individuals committed to environmental issues, and also the responses from persons living in LL areas (general public) could be related to sample self-selection (i.e. respondents who participated to the survey were averagely more committed than the overall population).

We also verified the presence of gender and age differences on our dependent variables, consistently with outcomes evidenced in the literature (Clayton et al., 2021). The MANOVA we run for this aim produced no significant gender or age differences in INS and EID scores, also considering their interaction with specific LLs.

3.2 NBS and Wellbeing

Perception of WBI and WBC was investigated with two different Correspondence Analyses.

3.2.1 Individual Well-being (WBI)

The Correspondence Analysis revealed that the two extracted dimensions explained 81.2% of the total inertia. The Chi-square test was significant ($\chi^2(40) = 110.431$, $p < .001$).

Table 4. Eigenvalues and appropriate dimensionality determination in the Correspondence Analysis.

Dimension s	Singular value	Inertia	Proportion explained %	Cumulative proportion %	Chi-Square
1	0.179	0.032	0.545	0.545	110.431 ($p < .001$)
2	0.125	0.016	0.267	0.812	
3	0.079	0.006	0.106	0.918	
4	0.067	0.005	0.078	0.995	
5	0.017	0.000	0.005	1.000	
Total		0.059	1.000	1.000	

The Chi-square of independence between the two variables (columns and rows) and the p-value are also reported.

The correspondence map (Figure 2) shows each category score on both dimensions (at once) for both LL and factors influencing well-being (at once). As measures of distance on the two interpreted dimensions, the scores enable a comparison of categories across variables in a two-dimensional space. Differently from correlation analyses, correspondence analysis is a standardized measure of relationship (in space/distance) between categories of multiple variables (in this case, two). It is important to note that the dimensions are empirically derived axes or eigenvectors, and not simply variables entered into the analysis.

Figure 2. Factors contributing to WBI (general public, 6 LLs, N=359).

Note: Empty circles (Factors influencing WBI) = 1: Recreation/Being outdoors for myself; 2: Recreation/Being outdoors with family members and friends; 3: Walk with a pet; 4: Feeling of belonging to the place; 5: Quality of natural environment (Clean air, water, etc.); 6: Weather stability (fewer extremes); 7: Nature contributing to my health; 8: Nature providing opportunities for foraging, hunting, fishing; 9: Income from nature/nature-based livelihoods.

Figure 2 shows that n°9 (green empty circle, top left) stands alone (corresponding to Income derived from nature/nature-based livelihoods), as such it is not associated with any LL (i.e. it was not chosen by any LL in particular) or other nature items. A possible explanation is that people who answered the survey were not using nature-based activities for their subsistence, and thus this factor did not influence their WBI.

We can also highlight that in the Tartu LL “Walking with a pet” is frequently chosen. The Beskydy LL and Murray Park LL are similar in terms of choices made, especially for the feeling of belonging to the place and weather stability (empty circles n°4 and n°6, respectively). The deep historical significance of a natural area for the local community enhances the feeling of belonging and increasing place attachment. The weather plays an important role in determining the use and enjoyment of a park. A possible explanation for choice similarities between Catalonia (rural-agricultural) and Sardinia (urban park) could be because both are Mediterranean regions, with demographically and morphologically similar territories. Specifically, it seems that all the factors listed, except for Income from nature/nature-based livelihoods (empty circle n°9) and Walk with a pet (empty circle n°3), contribute to their WBI.

Regarding the WBI of the key stakeholders sample, the Chi-square test indicate no significant differences between LLs for the majority of examined indicators (see Table 5).

Table 5. Factors influencing WBI in LLs (key stakeholders, N=68).

	N Beskydy		N Catalonia		N Hungary		N Sardinia		N Scotland		N Tartu		N Turku	
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
1. Recreation/ Being outdoors for myself	0	11	Na	Na	1	11	1	11	0	13	0	10	0	10
2. Recreation/ Being outdoors with family members and friends	0	11	Na	Na	1	11	1	11	0	13	0	10	1	9
3. Walk with a pet	6	5	Na	Na	6	6	7	5	3	10	5	5	8	2
4. Feeling of belonging to the place	5	6	Na	Na	4	8	6	6	1	12	1	8	1	9
5. Quality of natural environment (Clean air, water...	2	9	Na	Na	0	12	0	12	2	12	0	10	1	9
6. Weather stability (fewer extremes)	6	5	Na	Na	6	6	5	7	6	7	6	4	7	3
7. Nature contributing to my Health	2	9	Na	Na	4	8	1	11	1	12	1	9	3	7
8. Nature providing possibilities for foraging, hunting, fishing	5	6	Na	Na	7	5	6	6	2	11	5	5	4	6
9. Income from nature/nature based livelihoods	5	6	Na	Na	8	4	4	8	4	9	10	0	9	1

However, the Chi-square test revealed a significant difference between the LLs regarding income derived from nature or nature-based livelihoods ($\chi^2 < .01$) This suggests that some LL may have greater opportunities or economic benefits stemming from interaction with the natural environment compared to others. In particular, it

appears that users of the Murray Park LL increasingly recognise the numerous benefits, “providing access to forest products such as wood, fruit, and foraging opportunities” (see Figure 3). In the Sardinia LL, eight out of 12 stakeholders rated Income derived from nature/nature-based livelihoods as a factor that contributes to their individual well-being. This result can be explained by the fact that the majority of core stakeholders interviewed in the Sardinia LL are professionals working in associations dealing with NBS or who are involved with nature; hence many derive economic profit from nature-related activities.

Figure 3. Income derived from nature or nature-based livelihoods (key stakeholders, N=77).

Note: Differences across LLs between participants who have not flagged (on the left=0 on the x-axis) vs. flagged (on the right=1 on the x-axis)

For the other eight indicators, that no significant differences emerged between LLs indicates a relative homogeneity in WBI levels regarding these specific aspects. Catalonia did not answer this question. Nature contributing to one’s health highlighted both physical (walking, gardening, recreational activities) and mental aspects (e.g. stress release “some mental cleansing from all this green”).

3.2.2 Community Well-Being (WBC)

The Correspondence Analysis revealed that the two extracted dimensions explained 92.7% of the total inertia. The Chi-square test was significant ($\chi^2(25) = 62.866$, $p < .001$) (see Table 6).

Table 6. Eigenvalues and appropriate dimensionality determination in the Correspondence Analysis.

Dimension s	Singular value	Inertia	Proportion explained %	Cumulative proportion %	Chi-Square
1	0.192	0.037	0.695	0.695	62.866 (p<.001)
2	0.111	0.012	0.232	0.927	
3	0.058	0.003	0.064	0.991	
4	0.022	0.053	0.009	1.000	
Total		0.053	1.000	1.000	

Note: The Chi-square of independence between the two variables (columns and rows) and the p-value are also reported.

Figure 4 shows the correspondence map.

Figure 4. Factors contributing to WBC (general public, 6 LLs, N=359).

Note: Empty circles (Factors influencing Community Well-being) = 1: Building climate resilience (adapting to external shocks); 2: Halting biodiversity loss (protecting fauna, flora); 3: Economic prosperity/growth; 4: Human health; 5: Ecosystem health; 6: Community space.

Here we can observe that the Turku LL is not associated with other LLs in terms of similarity of choices made for WBC and is associated only with Economic prosperity/growth (empty circle n°3). We can observe also that the Sardinia LL is not associated with any particular LLs in terms of similarity of choices regarding factors associated with WBC, and the most chosen factors are Halting biodiversity loss (protecting fauna, and flora) and Ecosystem Health. The Beskydy LL and Catalonia LL are associated, and their most frequent factor contributing to WBC was the Building of climate resilience (empty circle n°1). Finally, participants from Murray Park LL and Tartu LL also made very similar choices regarding WBC: their most frequent choices

are Human Health and Community Space (empty circles n°4 and n°6, respectively). Additionally, Murray Park fostered a sense of community, encouraging social interaction and connection with nature.

The results of the Chi-square test among key stakeholders indicate that there are no significant differences among the LLs for the majority of indicators (see Table 7).

Table 7. Factors influencing WBC in LLs (key stakeholders, N=77).

	N Beskydy		N Catalonia		N Hungary		N Sardinia		N Scotland		N Tartu		N Turku	
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
1. Building climate resilience (adapting to external shocks)	3	8	0	8	4	8	4	8	3	8	3	7	4	6
2. Halting biodiversity loss (protecting fauna, flora)	3	6	2	6	2	10	2	10	0	11	1	9	2	8
3. Economic prosperity/growth	2	9	5	3	7	5	4	8	2	9	4	6	3	7
4. Human health	2	9	3	5	0	12	5	7	1	10	0	10	2	8
5. Ecosystem health	1	10	2	6	0	12	2	10	0	11	1	9	4	6
6. Community space	3	8	3	5	1	11	2	10	1	11	0	10	0	10

Although the Chi-square test revealed a slightly non-significant difference ($p=.056$), its value suggests minimal variation among LLs regarding human health. Respecting variations in health care systems, most LLs consider human health as one of the main factors that contribute to WBC (see Figure 5). Additionally, in the Hungary LL biodiversity was linked to ecosystem health, with an emphasis on interconnectedness. For the other five indicators, no significant differences emerged between LLs, i.e. overall homogeneity in WBC levels for those specific aspects.

Figure 5. Human health (key stakeholders, N=77).

Note: Differences across LLs between participants who have not flagged (on the left=0 on the x-axis) vs. flagged (on the right=1 on the x-axis)

This implies that in our sample, environmental issues are significantly linked to life and well-being needs.

3.3 Barriers to implementing NBS

A total of 13 barriers were considered essential from the literature review and initial expert consultations within the consortium. These barriers were further evaluated in the sample of key stakeholders and analysed using the Chi-square test to identify key barriers across LLs. Figure 6 illustrates the importance of these barriers. As reported, most related identified barriers had limited funding and low community interest along with limited skilled personnel. This implies significant barriers to administrative and financial support for NBS implementation. The second group of barriers concerns *conflicting policies and property rights* and relates to insufficient institutional support. *Conflicts with other species* was not considered as a significant barrier.

Figure 6. Barriers to implementing NBS (key stakeholders, 7 LLs, N=77).

Financial barriers and opportunities were also considered in more detail to follow previous findings on their importance. Key stakeholders assessed how financial mechanisms can reduce barriers to NBS implementation, and what stage of NBS implementation funding is essential to overcome this barrier (identified as a nodal point). Figure 7 indicates public subsidies (Sardinia, Beskydy, Scotland, Turku) as the most essential mechanisms to support NBS implementation. Catalonia LL and Tartu LL consider payment schemes, Hungary private donations, while the Scotland LL and Turku LL rely on independent funding. In Scotland, the lack of finance makes the Park Trust vulnerable to unforeseen events (such as legal fees or costs such as tree clearance after storms), which means the Park must apply for grants and sponsorships

for sustainable management and long-term support. In the Turku LL, value is attached to Pansio-Perno waterfront access as specified in the interview, as in the Finnish context, taxes are the main mechanism for funding environment-related measures and maintenance practices.

Figure 7. Mechanisms to financially support nature-based governance (key stakeholders, 7 LLs, .N=77).

4.4 Benefits of implementing NBS

Ten potential NBS benefits were identified for consortium deliberation. For each, respondents expressed their 7-step Likert scale evaluation (from 1=not at all important to 7=very important). Figure 8 reports the mean values for all LLs.

Figure 8. Benefits from NBS (key stakeholders, 7 LLs, N=77).

All LLs recognised and also valued 10 potential benefits. The Kruskal-Wallis tests confirmed that significant differences across regions only emerged in the case of climate risk prevention, which highlights the importance of climate risk between LLs.

Figure 9 shows all three phases: start-up operation and long-term support were considered equally essential in all LLs. While the Scotland LL and Tartu LL prioritize the long term, for Beskydy, Turku and Hungary start-up and operation is most important, while for Sardinia it's start up, and Catalonia indicates equal importance in all three phases. Preference thus varies depending on existing funding, capacity of public administrations and governance, and institutional conditions in studied regions.

Figure 9. Funding phases for NBS. (interviews, N=77)

Figure 10. Willingness to pay for improved relationship with nature (5 LLs, general public, N=359).

The general public sample also responded to a WTP question: how much would a respondent as an individual like to pay to improve their community relationship with

nature? In each region, the question was tailored to the specific NBS that the community would benefit from (e.g. water quantity in Beskydy). Data for Catalonia was not collected. WTP for six LL is displayed in Figure 10.

WTP to support NBS varied in six LLs. The Turku LL preference was for EUR 5–10, Beskydy and Sardinia LLs EUR 11–20, and EUR 21–50 in Murray Park (Scotland) LL. In the Sardinia LL, higher willingness may refer to an overall positive attitude to nature, which is consistent with the high scores for EID and INS in this sample (see par. 3.4). In particular, participants in the Sardinia LL believe that a community fee for nature and ecosystem maintenance is the most appropriate option. Preference for contributing more than EUR 50 in the Beskydy LL refers to voluntary work as a means of earmarking contributions (see Figure 11). These vary from independent funds in Murray Park Scotland and Turku, to community funds or local tax in Sardinia and Tartu.

Figure 11. Earmarking of voluntary contributions (5 LLs, general public, N=359).

3.5 Transformative potential of NBS

In addressing socio-political and environmental challenges, the transformative potential of NBS is an essential ingredient towards sustainability. LL key stakeholders were asked to prioritise up to four options (Figure 12). Overall results indicate Community-level engagement in social and collective action and social capital as the most related factors for transformative change, followed by openness to change and innovations in social practice, supporting partnerships and community strategies. The transformative potential of NBS has not been further explored in this report and will be subject to further qualitative analyses within Tasks 4.2. and 4.3.

Figure 12. Transformative potential of NBS (key stakeholders, 7 LLs, .N=77).

In summary, the nature-based relationship of the general public and stakeholders in the seven LLs are above the global average. This indicates high connectivity to nature, and a direct link to individual and community well-being. This is underlined by the 10 NBS benefits recognised as crucial in all LLs, including biodiversity, long-term sustainability, and connectivity to nature. The most frequent barriers in NBS implementation recognised by key stakeholders in the seven LL are limited funding, low community interest, and personnel with limited skilled, followed by conflicting policies related to insufficient institutional support. Conflicts with other than human species has not yet been experienced as a barrier, and the potential for novel funding options has to be further explored. Options for community payment and financial schemes to support NBS and willingness of the public to donate to NBS were indicated. Community-level engagement in social and collective action and social capital were found to be the most related transformative features of NBS. Further qualitative analyses are considered, particularly to explore the benefits and transformative potential of NBS. This report aims at understanding the existed NBS practices in seven LL sites and articulate and form hypotheses or questions for future, broader scale scientific work on the societal, environmental, and institutional conditions of NBS design and implementation. It is worth to notice that the answers from the in-depth interviews' sections are not reported and analysed in this report and are going to be investigated via lexicometric analysis with the aim to integrate and complement the highlighted findings.

4 Towards Nature-Based Governance

Based on the above characterisation of LLs (Table 1), NBS implementation practice (Chapter 3), and in the light of literature, more emphasis should be given to rectifying and further developing NBS governance that produces and reproduces vulnerability for human and non-human actors. For this, we propose a nature-based governance concept to expand the idea of nature-based solutions. This aims to also consider other non-human species and those human formations that are not typically involved in NBS governance processes as active co-creators of solutions.

4.1 Motivation to act for nature

The general public and key stakeholders in the seven LLs indicated high connectivity to nature and engagement in nature-based solutions. INS and EID were measured higher than factors commonly found in previous studies, which indicates high connectivity to nature. Eight factors were identified as essential for contributing to well-being at the individual level, all of which relate to nature and their values (such as outdoor activities with family and/or pet, feeling of belonging to the place; clean nature; weather stability; health; and foraging). For community well-being, human and ecosystem health dominated along with community space, climate resilience, halting biodiversity loss, and economic prosperity. This underlines the most preferred NBS benefits: long term sustainability, biodiversity and connection.

These characteristics are shown to build motivation to act for nature (Fornara et al. 2020). From the anthropocentric perspective, people can purposefully act for nature at the broader and general level, while other species act for their sustenance and livelihood and species-specific environments. From the non-anthropocentric perspective, non-human species make part of local ecosystems through numerous ecological relations (symbiosis, predation, etc.), so their activities can be seen as contributing to the well-being of multispecies communities. Non-human species seldom destabilise local ecosystems, with the exception of invasive species.

4.2 Institutional typology

Institutional arrangements aim to coordinate individual and social actions towards a jointly-agreed policy purpose and envisioned benefits. Our LLs results show that to a critical extent, NBS as institutions are (i) not yet functioning properly (existing NBS) for

human and non-human benefits, (ii) NBS are only partially established and not yet fully operable (incipient NBS), or (iii) NBS are still absent, but the need is envisioned by some actors (emerging NBS).

The assessment identified 13 barriers to NBS implementation. Barriers to administrative and financial support for NBS implementation have in particular been recognised as essential, along with *conflicting policies and property rights* potentially hindering the institutional setting. *Conflicts with other species* was not recorded in any of the seven LLs as a barrier. Lack of finance increases communities' vulnerability against unexpected events (such as climate or societal shocks), particularly in rural communities such as Catalonia, Scotland and Beskydy. The suggested mechanism to reduce those risks differs between LLs, depending on the specific local institutional set up.

As conventionally defined, **institutions** constitute a scaffold of formal rules, social norms and enforcement practices (North 2005) to help people participate, engage and coordinate their joint activities (Duru, 2014; Hiedanpää and Bromley 2016). To this end, and as our results show, rules-in-use (such as access to resource, withdrawal, management (Schlager & Ostrom, 1992), cost benefit sharing, internal control (Poteete et al., 2010, Kluvankova et al., 2013, Brnkalakova et al., 2022)), along with actors' rights (Peterson, 2000; Cardenas et al., 2013) are essential for shaping NBS, often even more so than property rights to the resource.

However, for other than human species the purpose is to identify and encompass pace and use-rights. The consideration of multispecies justice has demonstrated success in various contexts. For instance, in the Swiss Alps cross-sectoral information and actor contact networks have been essential for effective natural resource governance (Huber et al., 2022). Another experience is provided by three cases of institutional co-design of NBS with non-human agency to create institutions for non-human possession rights. In Kenya, non-profit organization Lion Guardians is co-designed as indigenous and science knowledge for coexistence with lions (Hazzach et al., 2014). Similarly, indigenous knowledge plays a critical role in attempts to protect the Atlantic salmon at Teno river in Finnish and Norwegian Lapland in the face of global environmental changes and potential national policy and management steps (Hiedanpää et al., 2020). A further example is the Barnacle goose accommodation fields in Eastern Finland, which represents a novel institution to reconfigure agro-management practices to share spatial use-rights between farmers and migratory bird species (Hiedanpää et al., 2023).

In essence, this refers to the right to have species-specific 'umwelt' – or 'self-world' as Godfrey-Smith (2024) has defined the concept – sustained for each local population that comprises the particular eco-social setting – urban, rural or coastal (see COEVOLVERS Deliverable 3.2). Species-specific umwelt refers to conditions where a non-human species can organise their physiology, and perception of the environment/environmental resources, activities/habits towards the environment in a way standard for their species. The challenge of including non-human rights is in knowing the needs of non-humans as well as their social representation. The institutional position of other species may be formalized in land-use orders, or may be based on local strategic plans and social norm/practice that aims for multispecies co-existence and justice. Institutions for nature-based governance are therefore collective action, which aim to shape policies and management practices to sustain NBS communities in multi-species cohabitation.

Governance modes encompass a diverse array of approaches and logic to managing natural resources and environmental issues (Pahl-Wostl, 2019, Ansell & Gash, 2007). The central aspects and logics of governance modes typically focus on decision-making within the governance system, e.g. command and control approaches towards more encouraging and collaborative frameworks that work with human nature and its complexities (Padovani & Pavan, 2012), such as participatory governance. Secondly, the logic of the governance system for neoliberal or market governance (Williamson, 1999) aims to coordinate private public partnerships of market transactions, such as compensation or payment schemes. However, market-oriented governance modes require markets and funding to sustain the long-term functioning of NBS. However, monetary incentives can support long-term sustainability if implemented as a local social norm (Hiedanpää and Borgström, 2014). The structural aspect considers the hybrid governance mode (Paavola et al., 2009) or network governance mode (Newig et al., 2010), which are both seen as adaptive collaborative cycles that aim to align institutional frameworks with natural conditions and enhance resilience (Hurlbert & Diaz, 2013) and are examples of well-functioning NBS. The hybrid governance mode, for example, has gained prominence by reflecting a shift towards experimental modes in urban sustainability governance (Xie & Bulkeley, 2020), exploring pathways for transitioning towards sustainable urban development (such as smart cities and low-carbon initiatives (Xie & Bulkeley, 2020)) and may be considered for Scotland, Turku and Tartu LLs. Polycentric governance mode is common in urban NBS (Ostrom et al., 1961, 2010, Ordonez, 2019) and multilevel governance (Tömmel & Verdun, 2013, Schroter et al., 2022) in spatially- and functionally- wider settings, and is promising for Sardinia LL. The e-governance mode implemented through digital technologies is a novel approach, which has gained attention by improving the fairness of public participation and decision-making processes in EU cities, transforming the relationship

between governments and citizens, enhancing transparency, and enabling more efficient governance practices in supporting NBS. E-governance is also a promising governance mode for nature-based governance and climate-smart collaboration via digital tools such as Beskydy LL's cross-border setting. Reflexivity is an ethical feature that can be integrated into these governance modes for justice and social cohesion considerations (Kabisch et al., 2016). Very specific is ritual governance that is emerging to coordinate rule-based multispecies interactions where non-humans hold recognition, voice and representation, i.e. possession rights (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2024).

Although the above-mentioned governance modes refer to stakeholder interactions, they rarely reflect co-creative approaches as means that bring together multiple stakeholders and public authorities for policy design and decision-making. It is believed that these may foster the cohabitation of problematic individual habits, social norms and organisational routines that impede governance modes' co-evolution and improvement.

4.3. Nature-based governance as governance mode

Despite recent increased interest in integrating other species into policymaking and under the conceptual umbrella of multispecies justice and sustainability, the governance mode – in addressing multispecies engagement and justice - has not yet been defined. Here we define the nature-based governance mode as a combination of existing governance modes *that acknowledge the intrinsic value of nature, aiming to align human activities along with other than human rights for sustainable development and long-term well-being*. Nature based governance thus (i) manifests the interconnection of physical and social (governance) domains, (ii) concerns vulnerable agencies (Honkasalo, 2018, Lecourt, 2002) *to the co-creation of NBS* by allocating umwelth rights to other than human species as discussed in section 4.2., and advances multispecies justice (Herrmann-Pillath et al. 2023). The benefit of such governance mode is to address sustainability challenges by working with nature to identify institutional solutions that can tweak the coevolution of institutions and the environment into more sustainable directions.

5 Conclusion

Addressing current socio-political challenges in NBS theory, design, and implementation practice encompasses various challenges and implementation barriers that hinder its effectiveness and scalability. This report provides insights into the institutional implementation of NBS in seven COEVOLVERS LLs.

High connectivity to nature and nature-based solutions in all seven LLs and the essential meaning of NBS for individual and community well-being indicate the promising potential of NBS for LLs communities, including vulnerable and other than human agencies. This forms a basis for conceptual work on nature-based governance co-creation. Nature-based governance expands the idea of nature-based solutions to consider other than human species as active in the co-creation of solutions for pressing sustainability challenges and a pathway to integrate environmental considerations, community needs, human and non-human vulnerability, and sustainability goals into decision-making processes. By capitalizing on opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and adaptive management, nature-based governance can contribute to more resilient and sustainable socio-ecological systems.

Despite the recent increased interest in integrating other species into policymaking, addressing multispecies engagement and justice has not yet been defined. Here we define nature-based governance and governance mode where multispecies' actions and perspectives are systematically addressed and recognized in order to plan institutional reconfigurations that respond to sustainability challenges and advance multispecies' justice. The nature-based governance mode concerns vulnerability among and between the human and other species introduced early in this report. The benefit of such governance mode is to address sustainability challenges by working with nature to identify institutional solutions that can tweak the coevolution of institutions and the environment in more sustainable directions.

COEVOLVERS LLs vary in their institutional structures and preparedness for nature-based governance transformative change. Key LL stakeholders are prepared, yet the institutional arrangements have been shown to not yet necessarily scaffold the needed change, or at least, they fail to do so consistently over different LLs. Better understanding about what transformative change means and how to achieve it is needed. Our assessment highlights the need to shift towards nature-based governance that involves and integrates both individual action and unorganised and organised social action as well as a diverse range of other species and important features of their living environments. This report identifies existing NBS practice and indicates potential institutional typology. As a work in progress, it will further inform the

institutional reconfiguration (D.4.2) and co-creation of nature-based governance models (D.4.3) for the seven COEVOLVERS LLs. This work is also subject to further elaboration in a scientific paper.

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